

MILITARY ART OF AMIR TEMUR

Eshboyev Dono Uzoq o`g`li

Termiz State University Faculty of History student.

Abstract: This article describes the military campaigns and tactics of our great grandfather Amir Temur during his lifetime. In addition, we will consider the new military units created by Amir Temur and their tasks.

Significant contribution of Amir Timur and his descendants, especially Babur, to the development of world western art. This was rightfully recognized by experts and generals. Considered a great commander and an innovative military organizer, Sahibqiron managed to create a disciplined army, to manage the units of the army wisely during the battle, to quickly send the western forces to the places where the fate of the battle would be decided, to eliminate the existing obstacles and pitfalls with entrepreneurship, and to keep the fighting spirit in the army at a high level. Amir Temur and the army of the Timurids gathered soldiers from the settled population engaged in farming, handicrafts and farming, as well as cattle herders. Along with the chief soldiers who formed the basis of the military forces, the infantry also served in the army. Sahibqiran was one of the first in the East to introduce a fire-ball (ra'd) to the army. During the Timurid period, other types of this weapon (zarbzhan, farangi, pot, etc.) became widespread. Special military units and divisions have been established to conduct combat operations in the mountainous regions. Amir Temur was the first in the history of world military work to introduce the order of deploying the army on the battlefield into 7 arms, as opposed to the traditional 5 arms. This news was later adopted by generals such as Tokhtamysh and Shaibani Khan. According to Ibn Arabshah, there were units of women in Sahibqiran's army, who stood in the same ranks as men and showed examples of heroism and fortitude.

Timurid's army was clearly organized in terms of numbers, its battle order was improved, it was equipped with the advanced weapons and equipment of its time, the units were distinguished from each other by uniforms, flags and flags. Such a distinction came in handy in commanding an army in battle. Defeat the enemy's defense in various ways, attack the opponent's big cities, lay siege to fortresses, fortresses and fortresses for a long time,

encircle the enemy's forces as widely as possible, conquer villages, cities, districts, regions one after another, destroy the enemy completely. Such practices as pursuing until maturity, appointing trusted people to lead the surrendered countries brought many victories to Amir Temur and the Timurids. Tactically, Amir Temur's army had its own characteristics. Reconnaissance is well organized, the necessary measures and measures are developed for the units to act as required on the battlefield or in the battle line, with special attention being paid to their rapid management during the battle. The Supreme Commander-in-Chief was responsible for the selection of ten, hundred, thousand and district commanders. Another great contribution of Sahibqiran to the development of military art was the introduction of the qunbul, a cavalry unit formed in order to protect the army's flanks from the enemy's attack during the battle and, in turn, bypass the enemy's forces from the side and attack them from behind. Such a new military unit did not exist in the army of such famous generals as Alexander, Hannibal, Genghis Khan, Louis XIV, Frederick the Great. It was also present in Shaibani Khan's army and it was called by the term tolyuma. After the announcement of a special order (tunqol) about the gathering of troops, according to the list compiled by the ruler, the warriors arrived at the gathering place with their horses, weapons, food, and fodder. Each soldier was given one bow, 30 arrows, one bow, one shield, one extra horse, rope, , leather bag, and one cauldron. Every 10 warriors were required to carry one tent, two shovels, one scythe, one saw, one ax, one ax and 100 coins. All 5 of Sarah's warriors are housed in one tent. The eleventh had a separate tent and 5 additional horses. Yuzbegi was also given a separate tent and 10 additional horses. In addition to the tent, Mingbegi is also equipped with an umbrella. 313 beks headed various divisions and units of the Sahibqiran army. The first 100 of them held the positions of tens, the second 100, and the third 100 thousand. Divisions - districts were headed by Amir Temur's children, grandsons and famous army chiefs. After a sufficient number of troops were gathered, it was inspected. During the Timurid era, it became a regular practice to inspect the army before a campaign or a battle and determine its fighting spirit and condition. ovgarta (hunting), which is recognized as a way of examining the combat condition of the bird, was effectively used.

The Timurids preferred to go on military campaigns in spring, summer and autumn seasons. According to the rule of travel, each commander, depending on his rank and position, acted in battle order with his units and divisions. A person who violates the law is severely punished. When the army entered the battlefield, the camp was fenced with carts, surrounded

by a trench, and guarded by guard units. In order to prevent chaos and confusion during marching or fighting, each unit, group, and unit has its own password - place. During the journey, the army acted in the following order of battle: Far ahead of the main forces was the outpost, followed by manglai (hiravul) (vanguard), barangar, juvangar, kol (center), chagdavul (rearguard). An ogruq (oboz) came in advance from the army. The commander-in-chief paid special attention to the choice of the battlefield. It was required that the battlefield should be flat, wide and convenient for the placement of troops. It was considered desirable for the battlefield to be close to the water and for the light of the sun to not fall into the eyes of the soldiers during the battle. During major battles, a battle flag with a half-moon shape attached to the end of the handle and decorated with flags was installed on the height of the supreme commander's palace. The progress of the battle was monitored from there. According to historical sources, Amir Temur's 12,000-strong army entered the battle in this order. The first encounter with the enemy was initiated by a guard engaged in espionage. After that, the advanced units of the right and left wings - barangar khiravuli and juvangar khiravuli - entered the battle with the main advanced unit - manglai. After Manglai, the remaining 2 units of barangar and juvangar - chapavul and shaghavul - moved one after the other. If these forces were not enough to defeat the enemy, the center (arm) (goal) under the leadership of the commander-in-chief (amir ulumaro) was thrown into a decisive attack: vdravul, karavul, manglai (khuravul). The tactical course of the huge battles in which the Sahibqiran army took part was as follows: the center of the army was divided into 40 divisions and obeyed the Supreme Commander-in-Chief. Of these units, 12 units, consisting of sara warriors, are located in the first row, and the remaining 28 units are located in the second and third rows. In front of the right side of the forty sections were the parts of princes, and in front of the left side were the parts of relatives and allies. In the barangay of the second row, 6 pieces with their predecessor - hirovul took place. Juvangari also had the same amount of land and land. In front of row 2 barangari and juvangari, there are parts of row 1 in the above order. In front of him, the main advance - manglai (or hiravuli buzurg) was moving. 2 detachments of light cavalry were busy protecting the army from surprise attacks and watching the movements of enemy forces.

Babur's army initially operated in the traditional 5 divisions. Later, serious changes were made to this battle order, the center (gol) was strengthened. The center was divided into the right-hand baraigyar chapavul and the left-hand, and acted as a row in front of the hossa

tobin, consisting of the right side and the left side. Hossa Tobin took a place in front of the personal guard, which was formed from the right and left, and served as 3 lines. The hossa tobin, made up of selected soldiers, was considered weaker than the center (gol) and stronger than the height. This military system, which brought many victories to the Timurids, underwent many changes during the Shaibani, Ashtarkhani and Central Asian khanates (Bukhara, Khiva, Ko'kan).

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